

Influence of Employees' Emotional Reactions on Employees Job Performance in Organizations - A Review

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Abstract

This study reviewed the influence of employees' emotional reactions on employees' job performance in organizations. The factors that determines employees' emotional reactions' used in this study are Personality, Culture, and Social Roles. The study reviewed 20 related articles, four textbook, and two reports on the effects of emotional reactions on employees' job performance. Secondary data was used that involved articles from journals, textbooks and reports. It was revealed that emotional reactions of employees (academics, as used in the study) has significant influence on employees' job performance at the workplace. It is however recommended that employees' emotions related matters such as employees' personality, culture and social roles etc. should not be taken for granted by organisational managers considering its sensitivity to employees' job performance which has multiplier effects on overall workplace productivity.

Keywords: Employees', Emotions, Personality, Culture and Organisations

INTRODUCTION

Employee emotions as used in this study means having the ability to love and be loved and achieving a sense of fulfillment in life. The factors that determines employees' emotional reactions' used in this study are Personality, Culture, Power and Social Roles (Suleman, Hussain, Syed, Parveen, Lodhi, & Mahmood, 2019).. Emotions are basically internal feelings or reactions to any situation. Emotions play a vital role in every person's life. Both positive and negative emotions affect an individual's personality or his professional career. An emotion is a mental and psychological state related to wide range of feelings, thoughts, and changes in body behaviors. As Emotion is subjectively variable, it is difficult to measure. For many of us, emotions are very personal states and many aspects of emotion seem insensible to us. Emotions mostly occurs under unpleasant situations, opposing of long held views, facing difficulty in getting something, a bad supportive role by other people with you etc.

An employees' ability to perform effectively in his job requires that he/she have to understand a complete and up-to-date job description for his/her position, and have to understand the job performance requirements and standards that are expected to be met (Suleman, Hussain, Syed, Parveen, Lodhi, & Mahmood, 2019).. The supervisor should review job description and performance requirements of the job. Employees' job performance refers to whether a person(s) performs their job well. Despite the confusion over how it should be exactly defined, performance is an extremely important criterion that relates to organizational outcomes and success.

Research Questions

- i. Is there any significant relationship between employees' personality and employees' job performance?
- ii. What are the influences of culture on employees' job performance?

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study is to review the influence of employees' emotional reactions on employees' job performance. Specifically, the study aimed to review:

- i. The relationship between employees' personality and employees' job performance in organizations
- ii. The influences of culture on employees' job performance in organizations

Hypothesis of the study

Ho¹ There is no significant relationship between employees' personality and employees' job performance in organizations.

Ho² Culture has no significant influence on employees' job performance in organization

Note: that being a review nature of the article none of the hypothesis is tested

Conceptual Review

Concept of Employee Job Performance

Employee job performance is defined as the outcome or contribution of employees to make them attain goals (Harrison 2016) while performance may be used to define what an organization has accomplished with respect to the process. Employee Job performance shows individual behaviors that contribute to achieve organizational objectives. Research proposed that high level of employee perception displays a high level of job performance. Employee job performance shows effectiveness and efficiency that make a payment to organizational goals. In the past employees were not able to make effective decisions because the system of the organization does not permit them to do this. According to Armstrong (2018) employee job performance is everything about the performance of employees in a firm or a company or an organization. It involves all aspects which directly or indirectly affect and relate to the work of the employees. Employee job performance is normally looked at in terms of outcomes. However, it can also be looked at in terms of behavior (Armstrong 2018).

Employee job performance is the realization of a task assigned to an employee based on his/her personal qualifications within reasonable limits. It is a function of the capacity, opportunity and desire to perform a task towards the realization of the organization goal in line with pre-determined criteria and the personal qualifications of the employee (Başaran, Cibere & Kantarci, 2020; Russ & Erdoğan, 2017; Pugh et al., 2016; & Ivancevich, Konopaske & Matteson, 2015).

Generally, job performance is considered as an assessment of the extent of an employee's accomplishments of the goals established by the organization and the acceptability of the employee's interpersonal behaviors relative to the norms of the organization (Arshad, Rasli, Arshad & Mohd, 2016). Moreover, high job performance of employees plays a crucial role in determining an organization's performance since highly performing individuals will be able to assist the organisation to achieve its strategic aims and sustaining the organisation's competitive advantage in general, while specifically, employees are willing to perform better to develop their career and enhance their skills as well as to influence management to retained them (Dessler, 2015). Hence the reason Human resource managers have high expectations concerning employee job performance by continuously monitoring employees' job performance through various performance management activities.

However, Employee's job performance is an indicator of organizational success, organizations today focus more on human resources whose efforts lead to better financial results, net sales and make organizations get better than before (Muhammad, 2017). Thus, the employee could be only satisfied when they feel themselves competent to perform their jobs, which is achieved through better training programs.

Furthermore, like in Hawthorne studies, and many other research work on productivity of worker highlighted the fact that employees who are perform well in their job will have higher job satisfaction, and thus supreme job retention than those who are not happy with their jobs. The term employee performance is typical to the Human Resource field and it is everything about the performance of employees in an organization. It involves all aspects which directly or indirectly affect and relate to the work of the employees. Hence, job performance of employees plays a crucial factor in determining an organisation performance. This is because highly performing individuals will be able to assist organisation to achieve its strategic aims thus sustaining the organisation competitive advantage.

In general, it can be deduced from the foregoing review that employee job performance has been associated with the ability of the individual employees realizing their respective work goals and fulfilling expectations as well as attaining job targets and/or accomplishing a standard that are set by their organizations. Therefore, Amir and Amen (2018) refer to employee job performance as what the organization hires to do the job and do it well.

In their contribution, Budiningsih, Dinarjo and Ashari (2017) find out that Nigerian universities are required to reach certain standards by improving their performance otherwise; a lot of problems will surface, including running the risk to close down the universities. This performance relates to the management or individual level which sees the human resource becoming the most determining factor to achieve the organizations' objectives. In fact, an abundance of resources such as infrastructures or physical facilities are made meaningless without the support of qualified human resources that directly disrupt the continuity of the daily operations. Within the framework of the professionals, good employee performance mirrors the ability to contribute through their works leading to the behavioral achievement that is in accordance with the goals of the organization. This means that Nigerian universities should gear more efforts in achieving set standards to avoid unforeseen circumstances.

Relatively, literature supports positive relationship in studies relating to employee job performance in different studies, but this study focused on the moderating effect of coworker support on the relationship between training effectiveness and employee job performance. The understanding is that when employees are been assisted by their co-workers, they get their skills improved and developed; progression in their skills will lead them to enhance their productivity and their team performance subsequently. Thus, they will complete their tasks on time and therefore their efficiency will too be increased. When performance increased it can help to increase job knowledge and skills (Amir & Amen, 2018). It also expands the intellect on overall personality of the employee which amounts to increase in the overall individual tasks performance and the organizational performance.

Basaran, Cibere and Kantarci (2020) stated that employee's job performance is measured against the performance standards set by the organization. There are a number of measures that can be taken into consideration when measuring performance for example using of profitability, efficiency, effectiveness, quality and productivity measures (Muhammad, 2017).

Profitability is the ability to earn profits consistently over a period of time. It is expressed as the ratio of gross profit to sales or return on capital employed (Wood & Stangster 2017). Efficiency and effectiveness- efficiency is the ability to produce the desired outcomes by using as minimal resources as possible while effectiveness is the ability of employees to meet the desired objectives or target (Amir and Amen, 2018). Productivities expressed as a ratio of output to that of input (Wood & Stangster 2017). It is a measure of how the individual, organization and industry converts input resources into goods and services. The measure of how much output is produced per unit of resources employed (Dessler, 2015). Quality is the characteristic of products or services that bear an ability to satisfy the stated or implied needs (Muhammad, 2017). It is increasingly achieving better products and services at a progressively more competitive price (Arshad, Rasli, Arshad & Mohd, 2016). Therefore it is the responsibility of the company managers to ensure that the organizations strive to and thus achieve high employee performance levels. This therefore implies that managers have to set the desired levels of employee performance for any periods in question. This they can do by for example setting goals and standards against which individual performance can be measured. However, we can deduce from above and define employee job performance as the aggregated financial or non- financial added value by the employees in contribution to the fulfillment both directly and indirectly to the targeted organizational goals. Employee Job performance is the most critical subject which plays an important role in accomplishing organizational performance (Wang & Chang, 2016).

In this study however, the researcher adopted the definition of employee job performance raised by (Iqbal, Ijaz, Latif & Mushtaq, 2015) that described employee job performance as the ability of individuals to achieve their respective work aims, then meet their expectations, achieve benchmarks or accomplish their organizational goals. However, the said authors did not segregate whether employee job performance is not a single unified construct but a multidimensional construct and whether job performance is the measurement of the quality and quantity of human capital and Job performance is affected by many situational factors such as environmental. This study will try achieve such and found out that job performance could be affected by other factors such as need to achievement, span of control, self-confidence, capacity, and interaction between these factors characteristics, organization itself, coworkers, and internal factors such as employee motivations, emotions, training facilities and beliefs that motivate them to reacts to situational factors.

However, the various definitions of employee performance stated above failed to segregate on the basis or nature of employee job such as academic and medical services or manufacturing sectors which could have helped in understanding the concept as exactly the way this study dwell to confirm. And whether or not employee job performance could be achieved jointly with other colleagues on the job or single-handedly. Therefore, it is on this background that this study adopted the definition given by Armstrong (2018) that employee job performance is everything about the performance of employees in a firm or a company or an organization. Performance is a major multidimensional construct aimed to achieve results and has a strong link to strategic goals of an organization. Therefore, providing proper strategies for employee job performance is one of great challenges among the managers to improve organizational performance and efficiencies (Russ & Erdoğan, 2017).

Empirical review on Emotional Reaction and Employee Job Performance

Emotional reaction is the attitudes of participants in respect to his job at workplace (Suleman, Hussain, Syed, Parveen, Lodhi & Mahmood, 2019).. A worker who has considerably gained skill and knowledge from the training will be eager to relate it on his/her job, thus bring positive reaction. To him emotional reaction could be a barometer for measuring employee's general attitude, expectations and motivation at work.

On the other hand, Mehay, Salas and Tick (2015) stated that having positive feelings in the strong service environment can contribute to cooperation, teamwork and increase performance. Thus, an emotion like anger, interest and trust is not immediate, nor is it prolonged like a mood; rather emotion is a brief incident of corresponding changes in mind and body which directly affects the employee's performance. Emotions directly influence decision making, creativity and interpersonal relations (Byrne, 2015) and consider three elements of emotions that are: anger, trust and interest. Anger is a basic human emotion that is experienced by all. Anger commonly happens under unpleasant situations, facing difficulty in getting something, opposing of long held views and a bad supportive role by other people with you etc. which all have multiplier effects on worker productivity in the workplace. These studies corroborate with the view of Al Kahtani (2016) on employee emotional intelligence and employee performance in the higher education institutions in Saudi Arabian issues related to employee emotion that employee emotion can lead either a higher or lower morale, which will impact the employees' performance positively or negatively. However in either case the studies did not indicate the level at which employee emotions affects individual performance. The current study will come out with a dependable conclusion by reviewing the issue to fill the existing gap.

Asrar-ul-Haq, Anwar and Hassan (2017) studied the impact of emotional intelligence on teachers' performance in higher education institutions of Pakistan. The researchers investigated the impact of emotions on teachers' job performance in the education sector of Pakistan. Sample size consists of 166 teachers from universities in the area of central Punjab, Pakistan. Reliability and validity of variables was tested through measurement model of PLS-SEM. It was reported that emotions has a significant impact on the teachers' job performance. Key research finding revealed that emotions, self-confidence, achievement, developing others and conflict management have a positive and significant relationship with the teachers' job performance. This study is strongly related to the one under investigation because it touches teaching profession and was carried out in a developing economy. Although the study used only 166 sample of teachers but still employed PLS-SEM to analyses its findings which made it not only current but relevant and reliable. However their study did not make any suggestion for future study so that future researchers may gear effort in that direction. Again the study uses academic and non-academic as well as casual staff in addition to using all universities in central Punjab when forming its population of study as against the current study that reviewed literature only on academics in relations to their personality and culture.

Another study by Tannenbaum, Mathieu, Salas and Cannon-Bowers (2015) on "Meeting trainees' expectations: The influence of training fulfillment on the development of commitment, self-efficacy examined the development of organizational commitment, academic self-efficacy, physical self-efficacy, and emotional reaction in a socialization-type training context with data collected from 666 military trainees in America. The hypotheses were that, tempolyee emotional reactions, and job performance would be related to the development of post-training attitudes. Support was obtained for each hypothesis. Employee performance was positively related to post-training organizational commitment, physical self-efficacy, academic self-efficacy, and emotions, even after pretraining attitudes and a set of individual variables were controlled. Trainee emotional reactions and employee performance were also related to the development of post-training attitudes. This literally means that training fulfilment, frustration by heavy work and self-efficacy plays a very important role that academic institutions of higher learning should be taking seriously. Since this study captured emotional reaction and training performance it will go a long way in helping managers in making inferences as the case may be. One strong criticism on their study is too much emphasis raise in relations to the development of post-training attitudes while totally neglecting employee pretraining and on the job emotional behaviour. This undermines the relevance of the study outcome.

Furthermore, Tsai (2019) conducted a study on "The important effect of employee's emotion management ability on his/her service behaviour in the international tourist hotel in Japan" to clarify the relationship between the employee's emotion management and service behaviour by analyzing 45 employees in the international tourist hotel, which involves high degrees of emotional labour that is more complex than in other industries. According to the empirical evidence, the ability of self-emotional appraisal and other's emotional appraisal become the important factors for in-role cooperative service behaviour and extra-role service behaviour. The practices can regard emotion management as the hint to predict employee's future service behaviour, and take it as a tool to choose staff with good service performance. However, the use of only 45 sample of the total population is too small for a study of this nature.

Similarly, a study conducted by Luthans, Avey, Avolio and Peterson (2017) titled “The development and resulting performance impact of positive psychological capital among employees of manufacturing industries in Norway concluded that when emotionally stable individuals successfully accomplish a challenging task, they are generally more confident in their abilities to accomplish the task again. They also reported in their research that physiological or emotional arousal and/or wellness may influence levels of personal efficacy. A classic example they gave is the organizational leader who provides caring emotional support and appreciation to employees to prevent burnout and to help keep employees mentally and physically fit that enhances their productivity at work. Although employee reaction also provides feedback on training style and content. An employee who has considerably gained skill and knowledge from the training will be willing to apply it on job, thus bring positive reaction (Saad & Mat, 2017). Emotions are pure human psychological phenomena. An employee is critically affected by their behaviors in the workplace. There are several studies in the literature aimed at affectivity and positive and negative affectivity. The main critic on their study is too much emphasis laid on psychological situation than employee internal emotions that trigger changes in his behaviour that has the resulting effect on performance.

Furthermore, Karkkola, Kuittinen, Hintsala, Ryyänen and Simonen (2018) in the study titled “Each one counts: Basic needs mediating the association between social support and vitality at work” the study provided new detailed information concerning the role of basic psychological and emotional needs in the relations between social support and work-related vitality. Drawing on the self-determination theory, the study hypothesized that support from both co-workers and a supervisor is associated with work-related vitality via the emotional needs of autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The participants were 109 employees in a preventive vocationally oriented intervention program. Results of the regression and bootstrapping analyses were consistent with the hypotheses, suggesting that each emotional need is essential in the indirect association of social support and vitality at work, regardless of the source of the support. However, the study did not include other equally important variables in line with basic need such as feeding and shelters which could be responsible for vitality at work, thus, this will be filled by the current study.

Thus, high emotional reaction leads to high relevant attitudes and behaviours as well as social integration among co-workers (Sloan & Geldenhuys, 2021). It also leads to employee engagement which has multiplier effect by not only affecting individual employees but by also impacting other team members. Emotional reaction broadens the path ways that are generated in goal pursuit of team members. One important consideration in emotional reaction is its resultant effects on employees as well as organizational outcomes. Based on the foregoing therefore the researcher developed the proposition that emotional reaction of employees have significant effect on job performances.

Genc and Gulertekin (2018) found in his study titled “Can hotel managers with social intelligence affect the emotions of employees?” using the multilevel model of emotional stability in Iowa manufacturing organizations. He investigates whether managers’ levels of social intelligence affect employees’ emotional labor and the emotional climate of top level managers of the workplace. In addition, the mediating effect of emotional labor on social intelligence and emotional climate is defined. A total of 276 surveys were distributed among the employees of a chain hotel in Istanbul. A structural equation modeling was used to explain the relationships between social intelligence, emotional labor, emotional climate and their effect on employee performance. The study revealed that social intelligence positively and significantly affects the relationships between and among employees and their productivity. Therefore researches of this nature today sheds more light and gives adequate review using recent literatures currently have been employed in this study. Since this study is on service industry the results when obtained can be compared and be used in filling existing gap by strengthening the literature.

Effect of Personality on employee job performance

The impact of personality traits on the Job performance of employees is absolutely clear and many organizations use this effect on their employees (Faeq, 2022). Personality is one of the major psychological factors affecting the human behavior looking at its important in the work place. A number of previous studies identified the importance of personality traits and found both advantages and disadvantages (Chen, 2019). Over the past couple of decades, personality has become a focal point in organizational research, leadership development and derailment. At most workplaces, people's personalities are not left at the door -- instead, they are a key factor in whether someone succeeds in a role. When you consider this, then, it makes sense why there's a rising field of study regarding personality as a predictor of job performance and success. Research supports the notion that personality can be used as a job performance indicator which led to the realization that perhaps when companies hire, they should consider other factors besides hard skills when filling a role (Diamantidis & Chatzoglou, 2019).

Nowadays, personality assessments are becoming increasingly popular as a method used during a company's recruitment and on-boarding process (Truong, 2019).. Understanding one's personality can help an employee modify behaviour at work, play to strengths, improve on weaknesses, interact with coworkers more effectively and ultimately lead to career success. “Personality matters for many reasons. One reason has to do with fit – how well a person's

personality fits the job, the team, and the overall organization. Poor fit is a major cause of conflict and turnover, Landis said. Personality will affect whether people are hired, promoted, derailed, will help others, be seen as a leader, and so on. Gaining an understanding of different personality traits can help workers grow and managers engage more effectively with their employees (Chen, 2019). Thus, personality is a person's distinctive patterns of thinking, feeling and behaving. It derives from a mix of innate dispositions and inclinations along with environmental factors and experiences." The concept encompasses how someone behaves over time instead of during a single instance. Generally, a person's core personality traits do not change drastically in adulthood. Sometimes people get fired because they make a bad decision, but oftentimes it's what you're repeatedly like across many situations —i.e., their personality —that drives a lot of the outcomes that we all experience in life,"

Not only does personality directly affect employees' performance ratings, it also shapes employees' positions in their social networks at work (Christensen, Golino & Silvia, 2020). Those positions help predict job performance, as well. As employees look to use what they know about their personalities to grow in their careers, the most important of the "big five" traits to focus on are conscientiousness and neuroticism. Highly conscientious, emotionally stable people tend to see more success at work. Some employees have a larger challenge than others, but they can exhibit a remarkable ability to change specific behaviors, especially when given insight into how their personality patterns are perceived.

Furthermore, taking a personality assessment can provide basic information that helps employees better understand their own inclinations and their colleagues' or managers' personalities. One insight is just getting a sense of how other people see you as an employee (Suleman, Hussain, Syed, Parveen, Lodhi, & Mahmood, 2019).. The areas that employees want to focus on are when there is a discrepancy between how you see themselves and how other people see them. Hence, some employees may misjudge their negative attributes, while others may underestimate their positive qualities. These misperceptions are very consequential for employees' own reputation at work. If employees sees themselves as assertive and others see them as overbearing, it can perpetuate a pattern of behavior that hurts own credibility. Similarly, if employee see himself or herself as an insecure person whereas others see him/her as quiet and humble, that discrepancy is also important to know. Therefore, identifying areas for improvement can help employees begin to make small changes towards improving their work performances (Truong, 2019).

Influence of Culture on employees' job performance

In simple terms, a positive work culture promotes employee productivity, engagement, and improved employee experience. A hostile work culture, in contrast, can affect productivity levels, increase turnover rate, and lead to employees feeling disconnected from their work and workplace (Khan, Ismail, Hussain & Alghazali, 2020).

According to Cherian, Gaikar, Paul and Pech (2021), organizational culture is a set of practices, values, and behaviors that employees experience in a workplace. An organization's culture is usually defined by the leadership and imbibed by the employees. Culture may include everything starting from the vision and mission, shared beliefs, rewards and recognition processes, to the style of communication and feedback, language used, and written and unwritten rules and customs followed within the workplace (Cherian, Gaikar, Paul & Pech (2021). There is a direct relationship between organizational culture and employee job performance, which is why this is a widely researched and discussed topic in the Human Resource fraternity. Some reasons why organizational culture matters are that:

- a) It helps create and maintain a unique identity for the organization
- b) It provides a sense of belonging and stability to the people in the organization
- c) Organizational culture helps retain top performers and valuable talent
- d) It creates a culture of engagement and increases employee productivity
- e) It keeps people happy and excited about the workplace

In the same vein, the culture that is prevalent within the organization is organically going to affect employee engagement and job performance every single day (Khan, Ismail, Hussain & Alghazali, 2020). How engaged and productive employees are at the workplace depends on how happy and in-place they feel about the culture. Organizations that practice an engaged culture see their employees happy, productive, and open (Sloan & Geldenhuys, 2021). As a result, such workplaces are able to retain their top talent and grow at a much faster rate. In simple terms, a positive work culture promotes productivity, engagement, and improved employee experience. A hostile work culture, in contrast, can affect productivity levels, increase turnover rate, and lead to employees feeling disconnected from their work and workplace.

When an organization promotes a culture of transparency, has clear expectations, provides continuous feedback, and offers the right recognition, employees can easily understand what is expected of them. A culture that allows employees to be open, honest, and independent nurtures efficiency and cooperation within teams (Cherian, Gaikar, Paul & Pech, 2021).. Together, well-defined organizational culture and employee job performance activities can make employees feel like they are valued and cherished within the organization, which affects their performance positively (Khan, Ismail, Hussain & Alghazali, 2020).

Conclusively, Studies strongly indicate that organizational culture is a competitive advantage that most companies ignore or are not aware of. But when used right, this can retain your top layer of talent, boost performance and productivity, and create self-reliant, independent, and responsible employees. Organizational culture and employee engagement go hand-in-hand. The strength of your corporate culture determines how successful you are as an organization. It is the foundation on which your employees will stand for the entire time they work for you.

A structured, transparent, and progressive work culture will help improve employee job performance and, as a result, improve employee performance levels too. So, if you want to build a high-performing workforce, the first thing you should invest in is improving your workplace culture. Changing organizational culture and employee engagement strategies is not an easy feat. However, it is definitely worth the investment.

Theoretical Consideration:

Attachment Theory: In developmental psychology, the theory that humans are born with a need to form a close emotional bond with a caregiver and that such a bond will develop during the first six months of a child's life if the caregiver is appropriately responsive. Developed by the British psychologist John Bowlby, the theory focused on the experience, expression, and regulation of emotions at both species (normative) and individual (person-specific) levels of analysis. Bowlby believed that the attachment system, as he and others called it, served two primary functions: to protect vulnerable individuals from potential threats or harm and to regulate negative emotions following threatening or harmful events. The normative component of attachment theory identifies the stimuli and contexts that normally evoke and terminate different kinds of emotions, as well as the sequence of emotions usually experienced following certain relational events. The individual-difference component addresses how people's personal histories of receiving care and support from attachment figures shape their goals, working models (i.e., interpersonal attitudes, expectations, and cognitive schemas), and coping strategies when emotion-eliciting events in relationships occur. Hence, attachment theory is adopted in this review considering its relevance and usefulness on the concepts under study.

Conceptual Framework of the study

Independent Variable

Fig_1: The conceptual framework developed by the researchers, 2023

Methodology

This study being conceptual study used secondary data which include peer reviewed published journal articles, text books and reports. Twenty published articles, four textbooks and two reports were reviewed that are relevant to the study. Attachment theory is employed as a powerful theory for understanding affect regulation. In this article, the researchers examine the role played by attachment orientation in shaping emotional reactions to interpersonal transactions within close relationships amongst academics.

CONCLUSION

The present study has provided additional evidence to the growing body of knowledge concerning the review of relationships between employees' emotional reaction and employees' job performance in organizations. Results from this study provide support to the key theoretical propositions. While there have been many review studies examining the underlying problems of emotional reactions and employees job performance, however the present study addressed the literature and theoretical gap on the variables. It also identified and filled the following gaps that hitherto existed in the employees' emotions literature.

Attachment theory identifies the stimuli and contexts that normally evoke and terminate different kinds of emotions, as well as the sequence of emotions usually experienced following certain relational events. The individual-difference component addresses how people's personal histories of receiving care and support from attachment figures shape their

goals, working models (i.e., interpersonal attitudes, expectations, and cognitive schemas), and coping strategies when emotion-eliciting events in relationships occur. In conclusion, the present study has added valuable theoretical and methodological ramifications to the growing body of knowledge in the field of industrial and organisational psychology, particularly human resources management.

Recommendations

Based on the new findings of this study, the following recommendations

- A. New findings of this study show that employee's emotional reaction is significantly related to employees' job performance. The affected organizations should be mindful of anything that would frustrate its staff. Anything that will remove anxiety, fear amongst staff should be discouraged and ensure trust, love and honesty excel. As this will help the in building confidence amongst the employees and propel their job performances as the case may be.
- B. It is recommended that the management should also pay additional attention to all factors that determines emotional reaction of employees that influence the employees' job performance in organizations – personality and culture as captured in this review study. The management should intensify efforts in preaching love and trust amongst employees to reduce the temper, dishonesty and lack of respect amongst the staff which probably propel negative emotional tendencies.

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